

Incorporating Social Media to Cope with Educational Inequalities in Southeast Asia A Five-Year Systematic Literature Review from 2019 to 2023

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Abstract

This initiative aims to explore the possible advantages of social media in education. A comprehensive analysis of several web tools has been conducted. Research indicates that social media offers several educational benefits. Web-based tools have been shown to promote communication among students and teachers. These devices enable instant communication between instructors and students, also, social media can boost student involvement. Students commonly report feeling frightened or bored in class and may feel more comfortable sharing their ideas and opinions on social media platforms. This research investigates the extent that social media applications promote teamwork by enabling students to work together towards a common objective. Online social technologies offer educational benefits and should be employed in classroom contexts.

Introduction

The web was a one-way communication channel, with specialists publishing factual information and knew how to design web sites. Users could only view webpages and could not edit or create information. The web has progressed from supplying read-only and static information resources to a more advanced platform. Social media platforms enable users to communicate, share, and update vast volumes of decentralized information. The fast expansion of social media is attributed to technological advancements such as increasing internet access, improved software tools, and advancements in computer and mobile technology have been remarkable. This form of media has become a commonplace in millions of people's everyday lives worldwide. It has a significant influence on both our personal and professional life. Social media has significantly impacted the way instructors and students teach and learn, given its widespread use among internet users.

Moreover, social networks connect individuals with similar interests, beliefs, activities, and experiences by exchanging news, images, and other content online. Videos and events, also social networks include a user's profile, social links, and other services. Social media is a relatively new addition to the Internet, and has experienced rapid development. It has now penetrated almost every area, including the educational environment. Therefore, online social networks are widely used by both students and instructors. Therefore, effective communication between instructors is crucial for a good learning experience. Whereas, effective communication between teachers and students is crucial for successful teaching and learning. Experts suggest that the lack of "connection" between teachers and students may contribute to this issue. Insufficient communication between teachers and students can lead to a lack of feedback and poor learning outcomes. Effective communication between both parties can address this issue.

Research Background

Information and Communication Technology (ICT) have the power to advance social progress as well as economic expansion. GDP and digital adoption were found to positively correlate, according to a study in 2020 focusing on digital technologies in 39 African nations (IEEE, 2024). In Africa, a 10 percent increase in mobile and internet connection results in a 2.5 percent per capita increase in GDP, while in the Arab states, GDP per capita can expand by 2.49 percent for every 10 percent increase in digitization (IEEE, 2024). A 10 percent increase in digital adoption can lead to a 0.8 percent boost in GDP per capita in the Asia-Pacific area (IEEE, 2024). Nations have benefited from investments in digital services and a population that is technologically aware. Due to unequal access to these technologies, some nations have encountered obstacles to economic development.

Most Internet users, particularly students, utilize social media to connect with friends, coworkers, peers, and family. This study will examine the potential benefits of networking tools in modern schooling. Instructors can use social media platforms to respond to student inquiries, publish homework assignments and lesson plans, and facilitate in-class conversations. As well as, send updates, organize events, and notify learners about special lectures, panel discussions, or guest speakers. Interaction between teachers and students can help students grasp and solve learning challenges more quickly. Students who seldom engage in class might actively engage in co-constructing their learning experience with their instructors and collaborate. Students may feel more at ease sharing information and ideas on social media platforms like Facebook, Twitter, or YouTube with friends and instructors. Providing students with supplementary learning resources in regular classrooms may be costly and difficult to organize. However, adopting social media can improve the learning process. Indeed, allowing students to participate in the many learning activities accessible on social learning platforms would serve to boost academic engagement by increasing the amount of time a student spends completing his homework or related school tasks. Furthermore, considering that many students frequently complain about being bored or frightened

at school, many social media sites' dynamic and participative character might be utilized to engage or re-engage bored or shy students.

According to many studies, students regularly report boredom at school due to uninteresting or irrelevant topics. Some students report boredom stemming from a lack of connection with instructors. Working and learning with peers is the most highly regarded educational strategy among instructors. Social media platforms may be utilized to create interactive and social learning activities in the classroom, such as discussions, debates, and group projects, to reduce boredom and increase participation. This would allow students to learn from one another and connect with others outside of school. Social media can facilitate more contacts between students and instructors by removing time and geographical obstacles. Students would have enough opportunity to ask questions, remark, and get feedback. As a result, they will have more opportunities to cultivate supportive connections with their instructors.

Social media promotes teamwork, which is a key benefit. Collaboration entails working together to attain common goals via intellectual, social, and mutual effort. Collaboration in an online learning community involves students working together in groups to achieve a shared objective. Collaborative learning encompasses several group-based teaching strategies, including cooperative learning. Effective cooperation involves three key elements: involvement, interaction, and synthesis. Collaboration in education demands more than just distributing responsibilities. Collaborative learning involves students working together on shared tasks rather than producing distinct pieces of a project. Social media platforms enable learners to exchange knowledge and resources from internal and external networks, emphasizing the value of cooperation in the learning process. Online learners, including students, instructors, and community members, may create their own curriculum and leverage collective knowledge. Social media may facilitate cooperation between students and instructors as well as among themselves. Therefore, collaboration of social media platforms allows for a shift in thinking about the energy and intelligence that may be created together, unlike traditional instructional models that focus on individual learning processes.

People without digital skills could find it difficult to get higher-paying employment. Furthermore, nations lacking reliable internet connection may encounter difficulties in their efforts to expand economically. Economic potential for disconnected people and places can be significantly impacted by the digital divide. In contrast, the digital divide may start to close and economic prospects may rise with investments in widespread infrastructure and internet access. Individuals who are disconnected cannot engage in remote or web-based work or fully participate in the global digital economy. Lack of digital literacy from educational inequalities also hinder job opportunities for new graduates. A certain level of digital competency is required for over 80 percent of middle-skill employment, according to research (IEEE, 2024). Higher skill and middle-level employment typically pay higher than lower-skilled ones. In addition, people without digital

skills are deprived of career opportunities. Furthermore, inequality can be reduced and economic outcomes can be improved with the aid of upskilling programs and digital skills training programs.

Scope of the Review

This systematic literature review will provide an overview of the current standpoints of incorporating social media towards educational inequalities, where the focus will be in Southeast Asia. This review should present the latest update, current situations, challenges, and upcoming opportunities within a five years period. This review will consist of research journals, research articles, research publications, reports and etc from two databases, which will in turn provide an in-depth view regarding social media influence with educational inequalities in Southeast Asia.

Research Objectives

To investigate Southeast Asia's source of inequalities which results in disparities which hinders children's education and see the feedback of using social media at an upper level of education. This literature review aims to explore and provide trends and movements that social media has towards bridging the gap between inequalities in education. This review will focus on identifying the problems, the processes, the methods and solutions that social media has to offer. Moreover, education in Southeast Asian countries are unequal, where students of different economic levels are offered different levels of educational exposure. Therefore, using social media, web, applications and etc should be able to help enhance and close the gap of reach for education for students at all levels.

Research Questions

1. Whether the use of social media will minimize students' gap and enhance learning opportunities ?
 - 1.1 What are the challenges ?
 - 1.2 What are the driving forces ?
 - 1.3 What are the digital solutions to close the gap and minimize digital divide relating to education inequalities ?

2. To what extent has social media influenced and changed the exposure in education and minimized reach for education ?
 - 2.1 What factors have changed and what remains the same ?
 - 2.2 What are the effects on digital divide ?

Theoretical Background

Role of Social Media and Digital Divide

Social media is digital technology that facilitates the exchange of concepts and data via online communities and networks, including text and images. Its user-generated material is commonly found on social media platforms, encouraging interaction through likes, shares, comments, and discussions. While social media is blamed for spreading hate speech and false information, it is also praised for aiding in the development of communities. In addition, social media plays a critical role in the marketing strategies of many businesses. Facebook, Instagram, WeChat and WhatsApp are the most popular social media networks used globally. The gap between people who have access to dependable internet connectivity and related technology and those who do not, known as the "digital divide," has a significant impact on society. The difference in access to information communication technology (ICT) between those who have it and those who do not is known as the "digital divide." (IEEE, 2024). The economy, social opportunity, educational equity, and many other sectors are all impacted by lack of internet access. The digital divide can have serious consequences, but there are several ways to help close the gap. Approximately 45.2 percent of homes worldwide do not have access to the internet, according to the United Nations Educational, Scientific, and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) (IEEE, 2024). Research on the subject of digital divides has demonstrated that certain groups of people and geographic areas are more likely to gain from digital technologies than others. Lack of access to these technologies but also because they lack the necessary knowledge and abilities to use them (Martinez and Mihelj, 2020).

The digital divide is most noticeable when considering other areas where inequality intersects, particularly with regard to race, gender, and class. According to a UNESCO survey, in comparison to men, women worldwide are 23 percent less likely to utilize mobile internet (IEEE, 2024). Women are 30 to 50 percent less likely than men to use the internet at all in South America, Asia, and Africa (IEEE, 2024). In isolated or rural locations lacking sufficient internet infrastructure, a large number of disconnected households reside. The cost of digital equipment or internet services is often beyond the means of many people. The US Department of Education reports that because of financial difficulties, students from low-income families are more likely to not have access to the internet (IEEE, 2024). Furthermore, in low-income or rural locations, internet service providers are less likely to invest in fiber broadband infrastructure—a process known as "digital redlining." (IEEE, 2024). When completing assignments or taking part in distance learning programs, students may encounter considerable obstacles. In addition to losing out on important employment prospects, people without dependable ICT access are unable to take part in the global digital economy. Furthermore, a society's ability to prevent further stratification, inequality, and disinformation can be greatly impacted by low digital literacy and lack of internet access.

Social relationships have become increasingly dependent on this technology. Social stratification has increased as a result of the digital divide, resulting in increased segregation and inequality. Therefore, it is critical that businesses, governments, and other establishments fund digital literacy programs in order to reduce disparities and enhance outcomes for all people. As more platforms have emerged to provide prospects for personal, professional, and business use, ICT services have become increasingly crucial in today's social interactions. Connectivity and communication between friends, relatives, and total strangers are made easier by social media platforms like Facebook, Instagram, and Twitter. Moreover, users of digital technologies can share information and voice their opinions. Those who lack access to modern technologies may find themselves lonely and lose out on social chances. When there are differences in internet access between communities, conflicts between connected and unconnected groups may get worse.

There is a noticeable digital divide among economic levels. Lower-income individuals lack the funds to purchase digital gadgets or pay for monthly internet access. The gaps between those who have access to the internet and those who do not will only widen as more people become connected. Users may not have access to the broadband infrastructure needed to use the internet if they reside in rural, isolated areas or less developed nations. Furthermore, having access to the internet gives individuals important social, educational, and professional options. People who are unable to access the internet miss out on these chances, which accentuates social divides, fuels segregation, and keeps economic disparities alive. Class tensions may arise as a result of this stratification, particularly in areas where affluent residents have access to digital technology while less fortunate ones have not. As well as the ability to use a computing device's physical components is a prerequisite for being considered digitally literate. Additionally, they need to know how to launch a variety of apps, including word processors, messaging apps, and web browsers. Additionally, a proficient digital user must be able to participate in online forums and recognize reliable sources of information. However, the digital gap is made worse by the fact that people without access to ICTs are unable to acquire digital literacy skills. The complexity and advancement of technology can make it harder to acquire certain abilities. Adults who lack digital literacy are so frequently significantly less inclined to utilize digital tools to their full potential.

In education, reliance on digital tools is growing more widespread. In addition to having to utilize computers for academic purposes such as researching scholarships, getting ready for standardized tests, and completing other assignments, colleges and universities frequently require their applicants to apply online. For many students, attending distant classes or finishing homework and research assignments requires the usage of an internet-enabled gadget. Some students do not have access to the technology and infrastructure needed to engage with online learning materials. Consequently, students may find it difficult to finish their schoolwork and lag behind their peers who have access to digital resources. Another significant element influencing

the educational digital divide is digital literacy. Without the ability to operate a device and navigate a web browser, a student is unable to perform internet-based assignments to a sufficient standard.

Education Inequalities in Southeast Asia

Wealth is the most significant factor for most countries. Education inequality is the consequence of it and is important since having more education frequently leads to better jobs with higher salaries and the ability to break trends of vulnerability and impoverishment (UNESCAP, n.d.). Education inequalities occur in nations where children are raised in unequal families and social disparity is high. These children arrive at school with different linguistic, cognitive, and cultural backgrounds and achievement is at unequal levels. Moreover, they make unequal decisions, which result in unequal educational and social outcomes. This also includes the unequal distribution of academic resources to socially excluded communities, such as school funding, experienced and qualified instructors, study materials, and technologies. These groups have typically experienced historical oppression and disadvantage. Schools with sufficient resources frequently refuse admission to members of these underrepresented groups. Social disparities in people's academic performance or effectiveness are caused by inequality, which affects social and economic mobility. There are several categories of disparity in schooling, including wealth, gender, social stratification, geography, occupation, and more.

Higher education frequently results in better employment and higher income (UNESCAP, n.d.). There are significant differences between nations, while the Republic of Korea's gross enrollment rates for higher education approached 97 percent in 2014, with Bangladesh and Afghanistan at 13.2 percent in 2012 and 3.7 percent in 2011 (UNESCAP, n.d.). Education leads to increased income, productivity, and improved job prospects. Lower educational quality and fewer years of schooling might impact an economy's productivity and growth. In general, increased academic attainment is often linked to increased salaries and living standards.

Inequality in higher education attainment and its decomposition, year 2007 - 2015.

Source: ESCAP calculations using data from the latest DHS and MICS surveys.

(UNESCAP, n.d.).

Results from the Demographic and Health Surveys (DHS) and the Multiple Indicator Cluster Surveys (MICS), showed in the D-index that inadequate access to schools and infrastructure might prevent students from finishing secondary education (UNESCAP, n.d.). Pink indicates that in Afghanistan and Tajikistan, females outweigh all other circumstances in inequality in terms of secondary education (UNESCAP, n.d.). In Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Mongolia, Myanmar, the Philippines, and Thailand, the chances of completing secondary schooling for a woman between the age of 20 and 35 years of age are greater than those of men (UNESCAP, n.d.). Higher education completion is influenced by household wealth and residence, while gender has a variable impact depending on the setting (UNESCAP, n.d.).

The role of ethnicity, religion and language in shaping inequality in education, year 2007 - 2015.

(UNESCAP, n.d.).

While household wealth remains the primary factor influencing inequality, ethnicity comes in second place for factors that contribute to higher education disparity especially for Laos, followed by Kazakhstan and Vietnam (UNESCAP, n.d.). Ethnicity and education are typically linked to other factors, such as living in a low-income or rural environment. Higher educational achievement among ethnic groups is associated with a greater likelihood of engaging in social, economic, and political life.

Southeast Asian nations need to prioritize education as a means of boosting their economies. Fundamentally, education is among the most important factors promoting human development and ensuring that each generation continues to evolve. However, one specific problem in education that Southeast Asia has is unequal access to education.

Educational issues in Southeast Asia have persisted over the years, governments are finding it difficult to establish new standards for education. According to the United Nations Development Programme, the calculation of education disparity involves analyzing the distribution of years of schooling among adult populations through nationally representative household surveys (Dip, 2020). The United Nations Human Development Report states that while the expected years of education in Cambodia and Laos are only 11.3 and 11.1 years, respectively, the percentage of the population who lacks formal education ranges from 20 percent to 30 percent (Dip, 2020). Furthermore, this indicates that a sizable portion of students and adults still do not have equal access to schooling.

Inequality in education already exists, and it is getting worse due to a lack of internet access. Much of the population in Southeast Asia has become economically fragile due to pandemics, and the region is still in the process of developing. Referring to the pandemic in 2020, schools shifted to using online platforms as a medium for education instead of onsite classes. Students must have access to technological devices, such as laptops, tablets, or smartphones, in order to pursue their education remotely when states implement "quarantine" and switch to distant learning. Students who live in large cities may not have an issue because they have access to these devices and an internet connection. Distance learning, however, poses a threat to students who live in remote places or cannot afford such instruments. The Brookings Institution reports that while the developing world employs radio and television to assist those without internet access, the majority of the developed world practices remote learning mostly through online platforms (Dip, 2020).

Share of countries responding to school closures with different forms of remote learning, by region

Source: Center for Global Development and the World Bank

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(Dip, 2020).

The absence of widespread internet connectivity is the primary obstacle to remote learning. The issue, sometimes known as the "digital divide," refers to disparities in internet device use or access. With high rates of internet penetration, Singapore, Brunei, and Malaysia have the highest levels of internet availability, while the other nations in Southeast Asia are still having difficulty providing internet service to the entire population (Dip, 2020).

Internet Penetration in Southeast Asia

Source World Bank

(Dip, 2020).

The majority of the students in rural places miss out on educational opportunities because they are unable to incorporate distance learning, especially for middle and primary school students, who cannot access the internet. Furthermore, purchasing digital devices for students might become optional, which would worsen the problem of educational solutions. Southeast Asia and UNESCO are working together to oversee remote education (Dip, 2020). In addition to solving the pandemic's effects, the area is advancing its societal solutions in the face of unforeseen occurrences that occurred to their nations.

Digital Inequality

The way we live, work, and communicate has changed significantly in the last few decades due to the quick development and expansion of technology. The emergence of the digital age has brought up a multitude of options for people, companies, and communities to engage and communicate on a worldwide level. There exist several individuals who are disadvantaged in the digital realm, as not everyone benefits equally from technology. Education outcomes are significantly impacted by this digital inequality, commonly referred to as the "digital divide," particularly for underprivileged students.

With the concentration on "digital divide," which is the difference between people who have access to digital technologies, examine the effects of digital inequality on educational outcomes and those who do not. The difference between people who use and have access to technology and those who do not is known as the "digital divide." Numerous factors, including age, geography, income, and education level, might be criticized for this disparity. Empirical research has extensively examined the correlation between the digital gap and academic achievements, indicating that students without access to technology face a disadvantage in comparison to their more fortunate counterparts.

Internet use by age

% of U.S. adults who say they use the internet, by age

(Perrin, 2021).

The Pew Research Center estimates that as of 2021, 15 percent of American adults do not use the internet, with those over 65 years old and those without a high school education having the greatest percentages of non-usage, therefore, people with low household earnings and those with education (Perrin, 2021). Due to the fact that many students use the internet and other digital tools to complete their assignments, obtain information, and communicate with teachers and classmates, not having access to technology can have a substantial negative impact on educational outcomes. The development of digital literacy abilities is also impacted by the digital divide. The ability to successfully access, assess, and use digital information is known as digital literacy (Glister, 1997).

Internet use by gender

% of U.S. adults who say they use the internet, by gender

(Perrin, 2021).

Internet usage by gender, men higher usage of the internet than women by approximately 3 percent (Perrin, 2021).

Internet use by income

% of U.S. adults who say they use the internet, by annual household income

(Perrin, 2021).

The higher the income, the higher internet usage. Based on the illustration, 80 percent of internet users are Americans with household income of higher than 75,000 USD (Perrin, 2021). On the contrary, approximately 30 percent are household income of less than 30,000 USD (Perrin, 2021).

Internet use by education

% of U.S. adults who use the internet, by education level

(Perrin, 2021).

College graduates use the internet the most, at approximately 80 percent, compared to lowest internet use by students below high school graduates at approximately 20 percent (Perrin, 2021).

Although there has been a long-standing effort to close the digital divide, not much has changed in that time. Increasing access to technology has been the goal of certain efforts, such as giving low-income families and schools computers and internet connection. The digital divide is a complicated issue that affects educational achievements significantly, especially for underprivileged children. Access to technology can be a barrier to the development of digital literacy skills and a source of inequality in schooling already present. There are actions to close the gap and guarantee that every student has equitable access to technology and the chance to acquire the digital skills required for success.

In order to educate and engage students, many schools and teachers now depend heavily on digital resources, making technology access a critical component of education. Not every

student has equal access to technology, which might negatively impact their academic achievement. Students from low-income households and those attending schools in economically challenged locations are less likely to have access to technology than their peers (IES, 2017). Without access to technology, students might not be able to acquire digital literacy skills, which would further disadvantage them. Initiatives like teaching teachers and children in digital literacy can improve student achievement (Paul, et al., 2004).

Although digital technology is now a necessary component of both modern life and education, not everyone has equal access to these resources. Lack of access to digital technology is common among minority and low-income students, which has a negative impact on educational outcomes and academic achievement. Lack of access to digital devices would certainly hinder student’s ability to acquire the digital literacy skills needed in the twenty-first century. Academic achievement is not dependent on having access to technology as digital resources and one’s capacity to use them efficiently are also critical.

Literacy and ICT access improve student’s learning capacity where communication moves towards computer-mediated communication, contents are relocated from books, magazines and journals to web sites, e-mail and messages instead, as well as students’ receptive and productive skills (Warschauer, 2003).

Literacy and ICT Access

	Literacy	ICT Access
Communication stage	Writing, print	Computer-mediated communication
Main Economic Era	Industrial capitalism	Informational-capitalism
Physical artifacts	Books, magazines, newspapers, journals	Computer
Organization of content	Novels, short stories, essays, articles, reports, poems, forms	Web sites, e-mail, instant messages
Receptive skills	Reading	Reading and multimedia interpretation, searching, navigating
Productive skills	Writing	Writing and multimedia authoring and publishing
Divides	A great literacy divide?	A digital divide?

(Warschauer, 2003).

Moreover, internet access rates are highest in the U.S. and Canada (181 Million people at 57.2 percent), followed by Europe (155 Million people at 21.3 percent) and lastly, Asia (144 Million people at 3.9 percent) (Warschauer, 2003).

Internet Access Rates, August 2001

Region	No. of People with Internet Access (millions)	Percentage of Population with Internet Access
U.S. and Canada	181	57.2
Europe	155	21.3
Latin America	25	4.8
Asia	144	3.9
Middle East	5	2.4
Africa	4	0.5
World	513	8.4

(Warschauer, 2003).

The significance of having access to technology in education has been brought to light by the COVID-19 epidemic. Lack of access to technology and the internet has grown to be an even larger obstacle to studying as more colleges and universities move towards remote learning. Apart from the digital divide, scholars have also concentrated on the "homework gap," which refers to the disparity in technology and internet accessibility that occurs outside of school hours. College students who possessed computers and internet connection at home demonstrated greater persistence and completion rates compared to their non-connected peers (Xu and Jaggars, 2013). Furthermore, the investigation discovered the relationship between academic achievement and digital literacy abilities was good. Employment growth and economic mobility are also impacted by the digital divide. Moreover, employees with digital skills were more likely than non-skilled workers to have steady employment and higher income (Brookings Institution, 2017).

Facts on Digital Divide & Resources Contributing to ICT Access

According to a World Bank survey, just 53 percent of households worldwide have access to the internet (World Bank Group, 2019). In the U.S., approximately 9 million students lack access to a device, such as a laptop or tablets, for at-home online study (IES, 2020). Also, 7 million American students lack access to broadband internet at home, which might make it

challenging for them to engage in online learning, according to the same survey (IES, 2020). Moreover, a 2017 study conducted in the European Union discovered that 43 percent of low-income families lacked internet connectivity, whereas just 5 percent of high-income households reported the same (European Commission, 2017).

Resources Contributing to ICT Access

(Warschauer, 2003).

Considering the effective use of ICT to access, adapt, and create knowledge, it requires physical resources, digital resources, human resources and social resources in order to effectively close the gap on digital divide (Warschauer, 2003).

Digital Divide Effects on Education, Educational Performance, Challenges and Opportunities

Digital Divide Effects on Education
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Limited Access to Technology and the Internet 2. Lower Academic Achievement 3. Social and Economic Disparities 4. Reduced Ability to Collaborate and Communicate 5. Limited Exposure to Digital Content 6. Reduced Access to Online Assessments

Bridging Digital Divide in Education

1. Increase Access to Technology and the Internet
2. Ensure Digital Literacy
3. Provide Support for At-Home Learning
4. Encourage Collaboration and Peer Support
5. Address Underlying Social and Economic Inequalities
6. Implement Flexible and Equitable Assessment
7. Provide Funding for Schools in Low-Income Areas
8. Foster Partnerships between Schools and the Community
9. Ensure Instructors Training
10. Conduct Research and Evaluation

Challenges to Bridging Digital Divide in Education

1. Lack of Access to Technology
2. Inadequate Infrastructure
3. Unequal Distribution of Resources
4. Digital Literacy Skills
5. Instructors Training
6. Language and Cultural Barriers
7. Lack of Support for Special Needs Students
8. Privacy and Security Concerns
9. Limited Connectivity in Remote Areas
10. Limited Technical Support
11. Technological Obsolescence
12. Limited Parental Involvement

Opportunities for Education with Digital Divide

1. Increase Access to Technology and Internet Connectivity
2. Address Affordability Issues
3. Provide Digital Literacy Training
4. Address Equity in Access to Digital Resources
5. Foster Collaboration and Sharing of Resources
6. Increase Funding for Digital Infrastructure
7. Expand Access to Digital Resources Outside of School
8. Increase Diversity in Technology and Education
9. Support Blended and Remote Learning
10. Address the Root Causes of Digital Inequality
11. Foster Partnerships between Schools and Community Organizations

Digital Divide Effects on Education

1. Limited Access to Technology and the Internet
2. Lower Academic Achievement
3. Social and Economic Disparities
4. Reduced Ability to Collaborate and Communicate
5. Limited Exposure to Digital Content
6. Reduced Access to Online Assessments

Limited Access to Technology and the Internet:

Students may find it difficult to finish projects and access online learning materials if they do not have access to computers, mobile phones, or the internet. This may result in a deficiency in participation and inspiration (Warschauer, 2003).

Lower Academic Achievement:

Research has demonstrated that students' academic performance and general educational results are negatively impacted by limited access to technology and the internet. Students who had access to technology and the internet at home performed better on tests and earned higher marks than those who did not (Warschauer and Matuchniak, 2010).

Social and Economic Disparities:

Education-related social and economic gaps may be made worse by digital inequality and the digital divide. Due to limited access to technology and the internet, students from minority or low-income families are more likely to have achievement gaps that are even more pronounced (Chinn and Fairlie, 2007).

Reduced Ability to Collaborate and Communicate:

Students who do not have access to technology or the internet may miss out on opportunities to work with peers and connect with teachers outside of the classroom (Kirschner and Karpinski, 2010).

Limited Exposure to Digital Content:

Lack of access to technology and the internet may prevent students from taking advantage of the wealth of digital content that is available online, such as interactive simulations, instructional films, and multimedia tools (Warschauer, Knobel, and Stone, 2004).

Reduced Access to Online Assessments:

Educational institutions are increasingly using online exams; nevertheless, students who lack access to technology or the internet could find it difficult to finish these tests (Warschauer and Matuchniak, 2010).

Effects of Digital Divide towards Educational Performance

Research has shown that limited access to technology and the internet can negatively effect academic attainment. Research indicates that students who lack access to technology and the internet at home have a major disadvantage over their classmates who have these advantages. Students with access to a home computer and internet performed better on reading and writing tests than those without (Warschauer and Matuchniak, 2010). Access to technology and the internet can affect student's long-term educational results, including attendance and completion rates. Access to the internet at home was associated with higher college attendance and completion rates, even after adjusting for parental wealth and educational achievement (Chetty et al., 2015). Digital inequality and the digital divide negatively affect education achievements, especially for low-income students.

Bridging Digital Divide in Education

Closing the digital gap is essential for guaranteeing equitable academic success for all students.

1. Increase Access to Technology and the Internet
2. Ensure Digital Literacy
3. Provide Support for At-Home Learning
4. Encourage Collaboration and Peer Support
5. Address Underlying Social and Economic Inequalities
6. Implement Flexible and Equitable Assessment
7. Provide Funding for Schools in Low-Income Areas
8. Foster Partnerships between Schools and the Community
9. Ensure Instructors Training
10. Conduct Research and Evaluation

Challenges to Bridging Digital Divide in Education

1. Lack of Access to Technology

2. Inadequate Infrastructure
3. Unequal Distribution of Resources
4. Digital Literacy Skills
5. Instructors Training
6. Language and Cultural Barriers
7. Lack of Support for Special Needs Students
8. Privacy and Security Concerns
9. Limited Connectivity in Remote Areas
10. Limited Technical Support
11. Technological Obsolescence
12. Limited Parental Involvement

Opportunities for Education with Digital Divide

1. Increase Access to Technology and Internet Connectivity
2. Address Affordability Issues
3. Provide Digital Literacy Training
4. Address Equity in Access to Digital Resources
5. Foster Collaboration and Sharing of Resources
6. Increase Funding for Digital Infrastructure
7. Expand Access to Digital Resources Outside of School
8. Increase Diversity in Technology and Education
9. Support Blended and Remote Learning
10. Address the Root Causes of Digital Inequality
11. Foster Partnerships between Schools and Community Organizations

Social Media Impact on Education

Exploring the relationship between social media and education reveals a complicated relationship that presents both opportunities and obstacles. Social media has transformed how we communicate, exchange information, and interact with people in the digital era. Digital spaces, first created for social interaction and networking, have now invaded many aspects of our life, including education. The integration of social media into education is not a new phenomenon. Educators saw the potential of social media platforms like Facebook, Twitter, and YouTube for teaching and learning as early as the mid-2000s (Saini and Mir, 2023). Over the years, the extent and depth of this integration have significantly changed, ushering in a new era of education marked by digital connectivity, collaboration, and information accessibility.

Social media platforms like Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, and LinkedIn have transformed how individuals communicate, exchange information, and connect with their surroundings. Social media has a significant and multifaceted impact in education, despite its widespread influence in modern culture. The intersection of social media and education has created complicated opportunities and problems, transforming the learning environment in new ways. This phenomena continues to grow, presenting educators, students, and politicians with both exciting opportunities and significant challenges. Social media has expanded education beyond physical location and time.

Social media has significantly changed education by democratizing access to information. The internet has become the ultimate library, with social media serving as a doorway to access this abundance of information. This accessibility has enabled learners to investigate numerous subjects and broaden their perspectives beyond what traditional textbooks could provide. Furthermore, social media's collaborative character has changed the educational experience. Facebook and Twitter connect people from all around the world, allowing for collaborative learning across borders. Social media has redefined peer-to-peer learning as it blurs physical and digital boundaries (Saini and Mir, 2023). The shift towards peer-driven learning enables students to take ownership of their education and improves critical thinking and problem-solving abilities. Global connectivity enhances learning and exposes individuals to many perspectives and cultures.

Positive Impacts of Social Media towards Education

Social media has significant potential for positive changes, particularly in education. Social media platforms are strong tools that may promote learning, stimulate collaboration, and broaden access to educational materials in this digital age. Every part of contemporary life has been impacted by social media, which has changed how we engage with one another, exchange information, and communicate. Social media's ability to link people across geographical and cultural borders is one of its most significant contributions to education. Social media platforms such as Facebook, Instagram, and Twitter allow educators and students worldwide to participate in insightful conversations, exchange personal stories, and obtain new insights on a range of topics. Due to its worldwide connectivity, education may be more accessible to students and a wider variety of resources and perspectives may become available. By using Twitter hashtags such as #EdChat and #GlobalEd, educators from all over the world may engage in discussions about innovative teaching techniques, exchange lesson plans, and get advice from one another (Saini and Mir, 2023). Professional development through collaboration has the potential to revitalize teaching methods and encourage the international dissemination of best practices. Websites such as Pinterest and YouTube provide an abundance of educational resources, ranging from lesson plans and instructional videos to suggestions for classroom decor (Saini and Mir, 2023). With education becoming learner-centered, social media platforms allow students to customize their educational paths to suit their unique interests and requirements. Moreover, social media

algorithms create content and recommendations based on information about users' interests and behavior. Students who find information personally meaningful to them are more likely to interact with and remember it.

Instructors can assign different discussion topics or tasks to students who need extra help or who perform exceptionally well in a particular subject by using platforms like Facebook groups or learning management systems. Support for self-directed education is another way that social media encourages personalized learning. Learners have access to an extensive selection of online courses and resources on platforms such as LinkedIn and Coursera, many of which are provided by prestigious universities and institutions (Saini and Mir, 2023). With the help of these platforms, people may take control of their own educational paths and select classes that suit their hobbies and professional objectives. The flexibility of online courses allows students to learn at their own speed, regardless of whether they have specific learning preferences or are balancing job and family responsibilities. Social media platforms also give students a place to demonstrate their abilities and expertise through digital badges and online portfolios, which can be beneficial for advancing their careers.

Social media can improve the classroom environment in addition to individualized learning by fostering real-time involvement and feedback. Social media platforms that are popular with younger generations, such as Instagram, TikTok, and Snapchat, can be used by educators to develop multimedia classes that are engaging and stimulating (Saini and Mir, 2023). Students can showcase their output of a subject by producing short films, interactive presentations, or infographics. This fosters creativity and critical thinking in addition to improving their digital literacy. Moreover, instructors can identify areas that need more clarification and assess students' understanding using online surveys, tests, and discussion forums. By allowing teachers to adjust their teaching strategies in real-time, this feedback loop keeps students informed and involved. Social media also gives students the ability to become active information producers and distributors as opposed to just being passive users. Students have the opportunity to share their research, insights, and creative endeavors with a worldwide audience through blogs, podcasts, and YouTube channels (Saini and Mir, 2023). When producing educational content, students must synthesize information, make concepts clear, and present it coherently. Social media has helped movements like #BlackLivesMatter and #MeToo gain attraction, leading to discussions about equity and social justice (Saini and Mir, 2023). Social media possesses the ability to close the gap in digital access to education and increase educational opportunities.

Social Media Platforms for Education

Education is becoming more data-driven and platform-based, online platforms have an impact on not just the fundamental processes of teaching and learning but also on how education is newly structured to fit student demands. Founded in 2012 at Stanford University, Coursera is a

for-profit platform that provides online courses to students all around the world (Dijck and Poell, 2018). It was supported by four American universities, and it collaborates with academic institutions across Europe, South America, and Asia (Dijck and Poell, 2018). Coursera provides free information to end users, similar to Facebook, Google, and other well-known platforms, therefore, students can sign up and watch lectures that have been videotaped, participate in online exercises, and take examinations (Dijck and Poell, 2018). Students are growing up surrounded by social connections that these platforms provide, both within and outside of schools, through connecting, liking, rating, and following one another. Facebook and similar platforms are built on mass personalization, enabling both many-to-many conversation and individualized content (Dijck and Poell, 2018). Additionally, a number of Google-developed platforms are widely used by students, providing free services like Gmail, Scholar, Books, and LibraryLink to students, instructors, and academic institutions (Dijck and Poell, 2018). Microsoft, Facebook, LinkedIn, Google, and other corporate platforms are able to strategically place themselves at the entrances to administrative, communication, and library infrastructures (Dijck and Poell, 2018).

Social media networks such as Facebook and Twitter are known as drivers of a new and socially engaged educational experience for students where it fosters the capacity for off-class discussions and also foster connections among students (Friesen and Low, 2012). A platform that is seen as helpful in enhancing self-study for students is Twitter, where students can have in-class and off-class discussions and can engage with other students to achieve their learning potential (Kassens-Noor, 2012).

Coursera

[Coursera Plus | Unlimited Access to 7,000+ Online Courses](#)

The image is a screenshot of the Coursera Plus website. At the top, there is a navigation bar with links for 'For Individuals', 'For Businesses', 'For Universities', and 'For Governments'. Below this is the Coursera logo and a search bar with the text 'What do you want to learn?'. To the right of the search bar are links for 'Online Degrees', 'Careers', 'Log In', and a 'Join for Free' button. The main content area features the 'coursera PLUS' logo. Below the logo, the text reads: 'Unlimited access to 7,000+ world-class courses, hands-on projects, and job-ready certificate programs—all included in your subscription'. This is followed by the price '\$59/month, cancel anytime' and a blue button that says 'Start 7-day Free Trial'. Below the button, it says 'or \$399/year with 14-day money-back guarantee'. To the right of the text is a photograph of a smiling man with glasses and a watch, wearing a green shirt. At the bottom of the page, it says 'Learn from 325+ leading universities and companies with Coursera Plus' and lists logos for Illinois, Duke, Google, Michigan, IBM, Vanderbilt University, and Johns Hopkins University.

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Methods

- Search Algorithm & Article Selection Process

This research is a systematic literature search across an academic database: SCOPUS - Academic Search Ultimate at National Institute of Development Administration Database.

The search was focused on literatures available in the database and then focused within a five years period, from 2019 - 2023.

Academic Journals: Year 2005-2024

Search Focus: Business and Management & Social Sciences

Number of Journals: 19 Journals

Keywords:

1. Social Media
2. Education
3. Inequalities
4. Digital Divide
5. Digital Inequalities
6. Social Inequalities

7. University Students
8. Media in Education
9. Teaching and Learning Strategies

Journals:

1. Sage Journals - Social Media and Society & New Media and Society
2. Information, Communication and Society
3. Technology in Society
4. Telecommunications Policy
5. Digital Geography and Society
6. Telematics and Informatics
7. Computers in Human Behavior
8. Cities
9. European Management Journal
10. Computers & Education
11. International Journal of Educational Research
12. Journal of King Saud University - Computer and Information Sciences

Academic Journals: Year 2019 - 2023

Search Focus: Business and Management & Social Sciences

Number of Journals: 11 Journals

Keywords:

1. Social Media
2. Education
3. Inequalities
4. Digital Divide
5. Digital Inequalities
6. Social Inequalities
7. University Students

Journals:

1. Sage Journals - New Media & Society
2. Information, Communication & Society
3. Technology in Society
4. Telecommunications Policy
5. Digital Geography and Society
6. Telematics and Informatics
7. Cities
8. European Management Journal

9. International Journal of Educational Research

Research Topics of Academic Journals: Year 2019 - 2023:

1. The first-level digital divide shifts from inequalities in physical access to inequalities in material access
Journal: Sage Journals - New Media & Society
Year: 2019
Search Terms: Social Media, Education, Inequalities, Digital Divide
Keywords in the Literature: Device diversity, devices, digital divide, digital inequality, first-level digital divide, Internet access, Internet outcomes, Internet skills, material access, peripherals
Methodology: Quantitative
Samples: 110,000 samples
Country of Focus: The Netherlands

2. To be or not to be algorithm aware: a question of a new digital divide?
Journal: Information, Communication and Society
Year: 2021
Search Terms: Social Media, Education, Inequalities, Digital Divide
Keywords in the Literature: Algorithms, algorithm awareness, internet use, digital divide, digital inequality, infrastructure
Methodology: Quantitative
Samples: 1,624 samples
Country of Focus: Norway

3. The social structuring of the digital gap in a developing country. The impact of computer and internet access opportunities on internet use in Thailand
Journal: Technology in Society
Year: 2020
Search Terms: Social Media, Education, Inequalities, Digital Divide
Keywords in the Literature: Resources and appropriation theory, Internet use, Physical access, Social inequality, Digital divide, Developing country

4. From digital divide to digital inclusion: Challenges for wide-ranging digitalization in Pakistan
Journal: Telecommunications Policy
Year: 2021
Search Terms: Social Media, Education, Inequalities, Digital Divide
Keywords in the Literature: Digital divide, Digital inclusion, Contextual factors, Policy and regulatory framework, The Pakistani society

Methodology: Quantitative
Samples: Systematic Review
Country of Focus: Pakistan

5. Social media among African students: Recentring typologies of non-use
Journal: Digital Geography and Society
Year: 2020
Search Terms: Social Media, Education, Inequalities, Digital Divide
Keywords in the Literature: Social media, Non-use, Typology, African students, Context
Methodology: Qualitative
Samples: 165 Interviews
Country of Focus: Africa
6. Social media and happiness nexus in the millennial generation
Journal: Telecommunications Policy
Year: 2022
Search Terms: Social Media, Education, Inequalities, Digital Divide
Keywords in the Literature: Facebook penetration, Happiness, Quantile regression
Methodology: Quantitative
Samples: Literature Review
7. Digital inequality in the Appalachian Ohio: Understanding how demographics, internet access, and skills can shape vital information use (VIU)
Journal: Telematics and Informatics
Year: 2020
Search Terms: Social Media, Education, Inequalities, Digital Divide
Keywords in the Literature: Internet, Digital divide, Digital literacy, Digital inequity, Rurality, Appalachia
Methodology: Quantitative
Samples: 197 Samples
Country of Focus: Ohio, USA
8. Social media for collaborative planning: A typology of support functions and challenges
Journal: Cities
Year: 2022
Search Terms: Social Media, Education, Inequalities, Digital Divide
Keywords in the Literature: Social media, Collaborative planning, Support functions, Participation, Communication

9. Work-related social media use: The mediating role of social media communication self-efficacy
Journal: European Management Journal
Year: 2022
Search Terms: Social Media, Education, Inequalities, Digital Divide
Keywords in the Literature: Self-efficacy, Social media, Employees' communication behavior, Work-related social media communication
Methodology: Quantitative
Samples: 1,179 Samples
Country of Focus: Finland

10. Digitalization of higher education to achieve sustainability: Investigating students' attitudes toward digitalization in Bangladesh
Journal: International Journal of Educational Research
Year: 2023
Search Terms: Social Media, Education, Inequalities, Digital Divide
Keywords in the Literature: Digitalization, Higher education, Technology, Learning, Digital divide, Bangladesh
Methodology: Qualitative
Samples: 32 Interviews
Country of Focus: Bangladesh

11. The power behind the screen: Educating competent technology users in the age of digitized inequality
Journal: International Journal of Educational Research
Year: 2022
Search Terms: Digital Inequalities, Social Inequalities, University Students
Keywords in the Literature: Power, Digital literacy, Digital competency, Race/ethnicity, Feminism, Indigenous studies

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